

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Graphene/Polymer Composites for Improved Barrier Performance

Dr Tom Raine, University of Manchester, UK

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Aim and Motivation

- Improve the barrier performance of industrial polymers using graphene as an impermeable filler

LAYER	MATERIAL	FUNCTION
FLEXSHIELD	NYLON 11	EXTERNAL FLUID BARRIER
FLEXTENSILE	CARBON STEEL	TENSILE STRENGTH LAYER
FLEXWEAR	NYLON 11	ANTI-WEAR LAYER
FLEXTENSILE	CARBON STEEL	TENSILE STRENGTH LAYER
FLEXWEAR	NYLON 11	ANTI-WEAR LAYER
FLEXLOK	CARBON STEEL	HOOP STRENGTH LAYER
FLEXBARRIER	NYLON 11 or PVDF	FLUID BARRIER
FLEXBODY	STAINLESS 316L	COLLAPSE RESISTANT LAYER

Proceedings of the ASME 2012 31st International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering OMAE2012 June 10-15, 2012, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Y. Bai and Q. Bai, *Subsea Engineering Handbook*, Chapter 26, pg 853-890.

Rationale and Testing

Graphene is impermeable – even to helium atoms

O. Leenaerts *et al.*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 2008, **93**, 193107.

Nielsen model diffusion

Diffusion Path l'

$$\tau = l' / l$$

$$D_C = D_0 / \tau$$

$$P_C = D_C S_C$$

Time-lag permeability testing method

N₂ sweep or manometer

Sample Preparation

1.

- Filtration of XG Sciences® M15 xGnP® from NMP dispersion
- Sandwich between Arkema Rilsan® BMNO PA11

2.

- Spray coat XG Sciences® M15 xGnP® from acetone dispersion onto both sides of CF
- Layer three CF layers and vacuum infuse with resin

1. PA11 Laminate Permeability

- CO_2 with 1.48% H_2S
- $T = 60\text{ }^\circ C$
- Supercritical at 10 Mpa
- 1 MPa = 10 bar

1. GNP Centre Permeability

$$\frac{1}{P_{\text{GNP}}} = \frac{1}{l_{\text{GNP}}} \left(\frac{l_{\text{composite}}}{P_{\text{composite}}} - \frac{l_{\text{composite}} - l_{\text{GNP}}}{P_{\text{PA11}}} \right)$$

2. CF Composite Permeability

- Upstream
 $p_{\text{CO}_2} \approx 1 \text{ bar}$
- Downstream
 $p_{\text{vac}} \approx 1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ bar}$
- $T = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Conclusions

- Laminate Composites:
 - Permeability of CO₂ reduced by an order of magnitude (> 90%) for pressures up to 40 MPa
 - Permeation of H₂S undetectable at 5 MPa
 - No detectable H₂S permeation for pressures up to 40 MPa for laminates with complete GNP coverage
- Carbon Fibre Composites:
 - 60% reduction in CO₂ permeation for 5 wt% GNP loading (with respect to CF mass)

Acknowledgements

Prof Peter Budd

Prof Ian Kinloch

Dr Oana Istrate

Dr Mark Bissett

Dr Xudan Yao

Dr Bernadette Craster

Mr Barney King

